

IOT BASED RESTAURANT MENU ORDERING SYSTEM

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Abstract:

To IoT based food ordering systems are replacing the traditional food ordering system in restaurants. IoT based food ordering systems are replacing the traditional food ordering system in restaurants. Instead of using paper-based menu cards, Restaurants are now installing touch screen displays on tables, so the customers can directly select the food items from the screen and order the food easily. Here in this project, we are building an IoT based smart restaurant project using Arduino. Here a TFT touch display is used to make the order and the HC-05 Bluetooth module is used to send the data to Arduino. Blynk app is used as an IoT platform where all the data is uploaded and can be monitored from anywhere in the world.